

Investigation of the influence of electron impact cross section from different databases on the simulation results of helium barrier discharge with dry air impurities

Constantinos Lazarou^{(*)1}, George E Georghiou¹

¹ FOSS Research Centre for Sustainable Energy, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, 1678, Cyprus

^(*) lazarou.constantinos@ucy.ac.cy

A validated numerical model developed for the study of helium barrier discharges in the presence of dry air impurities is presented in this paper. The model was used to study the influence of different helium databases (Biagi-v7.1, Biagi-v8.9, IST-Lisbon, Morgan and Phelps) on the simulation results. The calculations presented show that the discharge current can vary between $\pm 30\%$ in comparison to the validated model. This is attributed to the different electron impact cross sections of the databases.

The helium barrier discharge at atmospheric pressure has gained a lot of attention in recent years, due to its low production cost and numerous applications such as, plasma medicine, surface modification, air purification etc. In such discharges, the presence of air impurities is unavoidable and should be taken into account. These impurities significantly affect the plasma composition and consequently the discharge evolution.

With this in mind, a one dimensional plasma fluid model (PFM) was developed for the analytical description of the helium barrier discharge taking into account the presence of dry air impurities. The equations and boundary conditions used in the model are described in [1]. In the plasma chemistry, 27 species (e^- , He^+ , He_2^+ , N_2^+ , N_4^+ , O_2^+ , O_4^+ , O^- , O_2^- , O_3^- , He, He_m , He_2 , N, N_2 , $N_2(A)$, $N_2(B)$, $N_2(a)$, $N_2(C)$, O, $O(^1S)$, $O(^1D)$, O_2 , $O_2(a)$, $O_2(b)$, $O_2(v)$, O_3) and 167 reactions channels are considered. The kinetic scheme (reaction channels) are mainly taken from [2–4]. Additionally, the PFM requires the transport and rate coefficients as inputs. The transport parameters of the heavy species (neutral, excited and ions) are calculated from the kinetic theory of gases or experimentally. On the other hand, the transport coefficients of electrons and the rate coefficients associated with the collisions of electrons with the background gases (He, N_2 and O_2) are calculated from the electron energy distribution function (EEDF). In particular, these coefficients are calculated by averaging specific quantities and the electron impact cross section over the EEDF [5]. Consequently, the chosen EEDF and electron impact cross section significantly affect these parameters and subsequently the simulation results.

The EEDF can be calculated either by predefined functions (Maxwellian, Druyvesteyn and Generalized) or from the solution of Boltzmann's equation. In this study, the EEDF is determined from the solution of the Boltzmann's equation with the two term approximation [5]. However, input parameters are required such as the mole fraction of some species, gas temperature, ionization degree, electron impact cross section etc. The values of these parameters are mainly estimated from the experimental results. On the other hand, the electron impact cross sections are available on the open access LXcat website [6]. However, for each gas there are more than one databases concerning these cross sections. It is noted that the cross sections affect both the calculation of the EEDF and the swarm parameters (transport and rate coefficients). This indicates clearly their importance on the simulation results.

A prerequisite for the accurate simulation of the discharge is the completeness and consistency of the electron impact cross sections of the used database [7]. Complete refers to the ability of the used database to capture the most important electron processes while consistent means to be able to correctly estimate the experimental swarm parameters when this database is used as input in the Boltzmann solver [5]. For this study, five different complete and consistent databases (Biagi-v7.1, Biagi-v8.9, IST-Lisbon, Morgan and Phelps) are used to calculate the transport and rate coefficients [5,6]. These coefficients are subsequently used as input in the PFM. Initially, the Morgan database was used to validate the numerical model with the experimental results of [8] (using 125 ppm level of air impurity, 79 % of N_2 and 21 % of O_2), demonstrating good agreement. Subsequently, the discharge

current emanating from the different databases is obtained and compared in order to establish the effect of the databases on the discharge current. For these simulations the level of air impurities was set at 300 ppm.

The discharge current over a voltage cycle calculated using the numerical model and having as input parameters the transport and rate coefficients from the five different databases is presented in figure 1a. The current reference is considered that of Morgan database which is validated with experimental results. From Figure 1a, it can be observed that the discharge current from the different databases can vary by $\pm 30\%$, in comparison to that of Morgan's database.

In helium discharges, it is well known that the ion evolution depends heavily on the concentration of helium metastable atoms (He_m). In order to shed more light, the reaction rates of He_m production as calculated from the Boltzmann solver for different databases is presented in Figure 1b. As shown, these reaction rates depend on the mean electron energy (EE). Consequently, a higher increase of the reaction rate, leads to lower EE required in order for the He_m to reach the appropriate value for the participation in the reactions of ions production. Additionally, the lower EE required leads to a slower increase of the current value. As a result, the current reaches lower peak values but has a wider form. The above observation provides a comprehensive analysis of the current behaviour as presented in Figure 1a, justifying the lower and higher current peaks of Biagi-v7.1 and IST-Lisbon databases respectively.

Fig. 1: (a) Simulation current and applied voltage as a function of time and (b) excitation reaction rates of He_m as a function of the mean electron energy, for the different databases.

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